

Thermodynamical And Experimental Analysis of Design Parameters of a Heat Pipe Air Recuperator

*Emin Taner ELMAS

Department of Automotive Technology, Iğdır University, Turkey & Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences - Major Science Department of Bioengineering and Bio-Sciences, Iğdır University, Turkey

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*Corresponding author: Emin Taner ELMAS

Vocational School of Higher Education for Technical Sciences, Division of Motor Vehicles and Transportation Technologies, Department of Automotive Technology, Iğdır University, Turkey & Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences - Major Science Department of Bioengineering and Bio-Sciences, Iğdır University, Turkey Iğdır University, 76000 Iğdır – TURKEY

Abstract

This study is a follow up of the article named as “Design And Production of High Temperature Heat Pipe Heat Recovery Units”, and it contains the thermodynamical and experimental analysis of the design parameters of “Heat Pipe Air Recuperator” prototype of which project and design fundamentals presented and thereafter the production process has been completed by the previous mentioned study. The heat energy of the high temperature waste flue gases which are the exhaust product of a boiler or of an equipment producing heat energy has been recovered through the use of the designed “Heat Pipe Air Recuperator” which is a “High Temperature Heat Pipe Heat Recovery Unit”. This current study presents the thermodynamical and experimental analysis for the design parameters of Heat Pipe Air Recuperator.

Keywords: Heat pipe, heat pipe air recuperator, energy and fuel saving, waste heat recovery, exhaust gases, thermodynamical and experimental analysis

INTRODUCTION

The heat energy of the high temperature waste flue gases which are the exhaust product of a boiler or of an equipment producing heat energy has been recovered through the use of a “Heat Pipe Air Recuperator” which is a “High Temperature Heat Pipe Heat Recovery Unit”. This current study presents the thermodynamical and experimental analysis for the design parameters of “Heat Pipe Air Recuperator”.

An experimental setup consisting of flow - velocity control, temperature control systems, thermoregulator, heaters and fans has been established and assembled with the heat pipe air recuperator and its connection ducts, in order to realize the operating tests. The measurement and monitoring devices required for measuring the experiment implementation temperatures and flow rates has been provided and calibration processes were conducted.

The experimental setup system coupled with the heat pipe air recuperator and its connection ducts has been started, so the operating data have been provided. These data and the results obtained by the experiments shall be explained in detail at the following sections of this study.

The first part of the experimental setup system is connected to the bottom duct side which is also mounted with the heat pipe air recuperator and the second part of the experimental setup system is connected to the upper duct which is at the opposite side.

Identification of Measurement Probes and Sensors Used for Experiments

The temperature, flow rate – velocity measurement probes and sensors used for the experiments have been connected to a data logger device and indicated by Table 1.

Table 1. The measurement probes, sensors used for experiments and the related measurement parameters.

Name of Measurement Probe and Sensor	Function of Measurement Probe and Sensor	Measurement Unit	Measurement Parameter
1.1. Probe	Temperature Measurement	°C	Tg_o
2.1. Probe	Temperature Measurement	°C	Ta_i
3.1. Probe	Velocity Measurement	m/s	m_g
3.2. Probe	Temperature Measurement	°C	Tg_i
4.1. Probe	Velocity Measurement	m/s	m_a
4.2. Probe	Temperature Measurement	°C	Ta_o
C ₁ Sensor	Temperature Measurement	°C	Tg_i
C ₂ Sensor	Temperature Measurement	°C	Ta_o
S ₁ Sensor	Velocity Measurement (Frequency Adjustment for Motor rpm)	Hz	m_g, Vg_i
S ₂ Sensor	Velocity Measurement (Frequency Adjustment for Motor rpm)	Hz	m_a, Va_o

Recuperator outlet temperature of exhaust gas, Tg_o

Recuperator inlet temperature of ambient air, Ta_i

Mass flow rate of exhaust gas, m_g

Recuperator inlet temperature of exhaust gas, Tg_i

Mass flow rate of ambient air, m_a

Recuperator outlet temperature of ambient air, Ta_o

Recuperator inlet velocity of exhaust gas, Vg_i

Recuperator outlet velocity of ambient air, Va_o

Experimental Setup System

The experimental setup system established to realize the thermodynamical and experimental analysis for the design parameters of Heat Pipe Air Recuperator is shown in Fig. 2, the flow directions for exhaust gas and ambient air through the experimental setup system of Heat Pipe Air Recuperator is shown in Fig.3. The control panel and the connection detail for measurement probes, sensors, heaters, motors and fans are indicated on Fig.4. The perspective view for complete experimental setup system and Heat Pipe Air Recuperator is shown in Fig.5.

Fig 2. The Experimental Setup System of Heat Pipe Air Recuperator

SSS

Fig.3. The Flow Directions for Exhaust Gas and Ambient Air through the Experimental Setup System of Heat Pipe Air Recuperator

Fig. 4. The Control Panel and the Connection Detail for Measurement Probes, Sensors, Heaters, Motors and Fans

Fig.5. The Perspective View for Complete Experimental Setup System and Heat Pipe Air Recuperator

Measurement Uncertainty Analysis and its Impact on the Results

The calibrations of measurement probes and sensors used for the experiments have been carried out in order to ensure the accuracy of experimental results.

The measurement uncertainty analysis has been realized for the probes during the calibration process and a calibration equation has been obtained accordingly in order to state the measurement uncertainty and so, the calibration equation is written as follows:

$$y = 0.014 + x - 1.13 \cdot 10^{-4} x^2 + 8.88 \cdot 10^{-7} x^3 \quad (1)$$

The data provided by the experiments have been corrected by applying measurement uncertainty analysis as described above and Eq.1. Therefore, it is definitely possible to say that the measurement results obtained by the experiments are completely reliable and similarly it is also possible to say that the recuperator effectiveness rates are absolutely correct.

Results and Discussion

Effectiveness of Heat Pipe Air Recuperator

The various operating cases of heat pipe air recuperator can be obtained by applying various operating parameters such as temperature, flow rate, capacity and effectiveness. The values for the effectiveness rate can be determined by Eq. 5

The other related equations are as follows:

$$Q_{\text{Total}} = m_g \times (h_{g_i} - h_{g_o}) = m_g \times c_{p_g} \times (T_{g_i} - T_{g_o}) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{\text{Total}} = m_a \times (h_{a_o} - h_{a_i}) = m_a \times c_{p_a} \times (T_{a_o} - T_{a_i}) \quad (3)$$

The maximum capacity rate of heated ambient air obtained by the recuperator can be stated by Eq. 4

$$Q_{\text{Total}} = m_a \times c_{p_a} \times (T_{g_i} - T_{a_i}) \quad (4)$$

Eq.3 is divided by Eq.4 and the following equation will be obtained;

$$E = \frac{m_a \times c_{p_a} \times (T_{a_o} - T_{a_i})}{m_a \times c_{p_a} \times (T_{g_i} - T_{a_i})} \times 100 \%$$

assuming that the specific heats are constant;

$$E = \frac{(T_{a_o} - T_{a_i})}{(T_{g_i} - T_{a_i})} \times 100 \% \quad (5)$$

E, is the % effectiveness rate of heat pipe air recuperator.

The effectiveness rate , E, described with Eq. 5 can be calculated by using the recuperator design values mentioned as follows:

$$T_{g_i} = 260 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_{g_o} = 177 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_{a_i} = 27 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_{a_o} = 122 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$$

The above temperature values are substituted in Eq. 5 and the effectiveness is calculated as below.

$$E = \frac{122 - 27}{260 - 27} \times 100$$

$$E = 40.7725 \%$$

The above calculated effectiveness value can be approximately accepted as 41% and, therefore the effectiveness value of heat pipe air recuperator is E = 41% at design conditions.

The other effectiveness rates are obtained by the experimental tests depending upon the recuperator operating parameters and stated by the following tables.

The Data Tables Obtained by Experiments

The data obtained by the experiments have been stated by the below tables.

These tables have been organized by commissioning the H₁₋₁, H₁₋₂, H₁₋₃, H₁₋₄ and H₂ heater groups providing various particular operating temperature conditions for heat pipe air recuperator.

The flow rates for exhaust gas and ambient air are adjusted by the M₁, M₂ motor frequency rates and rpm values and these flow rates are then combined together with the changing temperature values. As the heater groups start and stop step by step, the motor frequency and rpm values are adjusted gradually decreasing and increasing. Therefore, a lot of combination of temperature and flow rates can be obtained by this method.

The obtained data and parameters of 31 experimental operations are summarized by the below tables (Table 2 – Table 32). These tables present the corrected measured data according to the procedure of measurement uncertainty analysis and these values indicated on the below tables are the “verified accurate results”. Table 33 and Table 34 present the design parameters and results either exhaust gas or air used for the tests, respectively.

Table 2. Parameters and Experimental Data Results– 1

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.064
m_a	kg/s	0.065
T_{g_i}	°C	24.96
T_{g_o}	°C	24.26
T_{a_i}	°C	24.18
T_{a_o}	°C	24.56
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	298.52
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	297.85
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	297.77
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	298.13
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.0331
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	48.72

Table 3. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 2

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.062
m_a	kg/s	0.062
T_{g_i}	°C	60.70
T_{g_o}	°C	54.22
T_{a_i}	°C	26.80
T_{a_o}	°C	28.45
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	334.52
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	327.97
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	300.28
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	301.93
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.2542
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	4.87

Table 4. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 3

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.084
m_a	kg/s	0.084
T_{g_i}	°C	23.07
T_{g_o}	°C	22.47
T_{a_i}	°C	21.80
T_{a_o}	°C	22.37
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	296.70
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	296.13
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	295.48
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	296.03
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.0470
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	44.88

Table 5. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 4

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.079
m_a	kg/s	0.140
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	76.75
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	67.77
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.32
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.95
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	350.76
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	341.67
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.86
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	300.42
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4682
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	3.17

Table 6. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 5

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.068
m_a	kg/s	0.140
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	79.25
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	70.36
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.61
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	27.95
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	353.29
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	344.29
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	299.14
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	301.43
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4663
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	4.37

Table 7. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 6

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.072
m_a	kg/s	0.139
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	81.75
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	73.65
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.95
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	27.95
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	355.82
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	347.62
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	299.46
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	301.43
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4321
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	3.59

Table 8. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 7

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.073
m_a	kg/s	0.137
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	82.75
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	75.00
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.32
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	28.95
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	356.84
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	348.99
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	299.82
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	302.44
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4659
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	4.67

Table 9. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 8

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.053
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	87.65
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	71.95
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	32.07
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	41.89
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	361.80
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	345.90
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	305.59
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	315.51
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.6285
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	17.67

Table10. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 9

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.053
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	87.35
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	72.05
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	29.30
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	38.90
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	361.50
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	346.00
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	302.79
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	312.49
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.6135
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	16.54

Table 11. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 10

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.054
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	87.15
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	72.15
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	27.97
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	37.90
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	361.29
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	346.11
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	301.45
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	311.48
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.6199
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	16.78

Table 12. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 11

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.054
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	87.15
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	72.95
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	27.11
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	36.91
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	361.29
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	346.92
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	300.58
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	310.48
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5978
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	16.32

Table 13. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 12

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.054
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	87.65
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	73.45
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.31
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	34.92
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	361.80
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	347.42
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	299.81
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	308.47
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5645
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	14.03

Table 14. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 13

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.054
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	88.35
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	74.95
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.65
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	33.92
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	362.51
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	348.94
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	299.18
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	307.46
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5356
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	13.18

Table 15. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 14

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.054
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	88.75
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	75.15
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.42
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	33.33
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	362.92
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	349.14
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.96
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	306.86
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5302
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	12.49

Table 16. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 15

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.045
m_a	kg/s	0.054
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	94.46
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	81.24
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	24.93
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	32.33
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	368.70
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	355.31
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.49
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	305.85
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4999
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	10.65

Table 17. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 16

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	90.95
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	77.84
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	23.96
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	31.63
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	365.15
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	351.87
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	297.56
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	305.14
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5138
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	11.45

Table 18. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 17

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	91.15
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	78.34
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	24.73
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	31.24
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	365.35
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	352.37
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.30
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	304.75
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4759
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	9.81

Table 19. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 18

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	93.16
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	80.74
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	24.56
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	30.84
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	367.39
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	354.80
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.13
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	304.35
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4606
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	9.15

Table 20. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 19

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	°C	92.25
T_{g_o}	°C	79.64
T_{a_i}	°C	24.61
T_{a_o}	°C	30.54
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	366.46
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	353.69
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.18
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	304.04
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4548
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	8.77

Table 21. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 20

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.045
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	°C	93.36
T_{g_o}	°C	82.34
T_{a_i}	°C	24.81
T_{a_o}	°C	30.34
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	367.59
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	356.42
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.37
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	303.84
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4017
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	8.07

Table 22. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 21

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.044
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	°C	104.50
T_{g_o}	°C	86.24
T_{a_i}	°C	24.67
T_{a_o}	°C	30.24
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	378.89
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	360.37
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.24
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	303.74
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5586
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	6.97

Table 23. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 22

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.045
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	96.06
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	83.34
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	24.52
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	30.04
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	370.33
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	357.44
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.10
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	303.54
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4396
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	7.72

Table 24. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 23

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.046
m_a	kg/s	0.055
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	94.76
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	82.04
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	24.49
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	30.04
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	369.01
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	356.12
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.07
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	303.54
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4468
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	7.90

Table 25. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 24

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.077
m_a	kg/s	0.084
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	67.28
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	58.20
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	30.77
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	37.11
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	341.18
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	332.00
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	304.28
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	310.68
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.6222
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	17.37

Table 26. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 25

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.077
m_a	kg/s	0.085
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	67.78
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	58.90
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	28.60
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	35.02
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	341.68
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	332.70
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	302.08
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	308.57
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.6215
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	16.39

Table 27. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 26

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.076
m_a	kg/s	0.085
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	69.17
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	60.09
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.91
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	33.43
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	343.09
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	333.91
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	300.38
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	306.96
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.6284
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	15.43

Table 28. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 27

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.076
m_a	kg/s	0.085
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	69.47
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	60.89
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.46
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	32.43
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	343.39
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	334.72
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	299.95
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	305.95
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5844
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	13.88

Table 29. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 28

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.076
m_a	kg/s	0.085
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	69.87
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	61.49
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.05
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	31.63
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	343.80
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	335.32
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	299.56
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	305.14
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5593
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	12.74

Table 30. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 29

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.076
m_a	kg/s	0.086
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	70.67
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	62.49
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.10
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	30.44
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	344.61
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	336.33
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.65
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	303.94
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.5421
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	11.72

Table 31. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 30

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.076
m_a	kg/s	0.086
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	71.27
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	63.58
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.20
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	29.74
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	345.22
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	337.44
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.75
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	303.23
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4882
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	9.85

Table 32. Parameters and Experimental Data Results – 31

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results
m_g	kg/s	0.076
m_a	kg/s	0.086
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	70.77
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	63.68
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	25.28
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	29.44
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	344.71
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	337.54
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	298.82
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	302.93
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	0.4491
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	9.14

Table 33. Design Parameters and Results if Exhaust Gas is used for the Tests

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results for Design Parameters
m_g	kg/s	0.274
m_a	kg/s	0.274
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	267.99
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	178.40
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.95
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	122
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	619.53
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	513.98
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	300.42
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	396.67
Q_{Total} (Gas Side)	kW	28.9207
Q_{Total} (Air Side)	kW	26.3725
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	27.6466
Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	39.44

Table 34. Design Parameters and Results if Air s is used for the Tests

Measurement Parameter	Measurement Unit	Verified Accurate Results for Design Parameters
m_g	kg/s	0.274
m_a	kg/s	0.274
T_{g_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	267.99
T_{g_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	178.40
T_{a_i}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	26.95
T_{a_o}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	122
h_{g_i}	kJ/kg	546.77
h_{g_o}	kJ/kg	454.24
h_{a_i}	kJ/kg	300.42
h_{a_o}	kJ/kg	396.67
Q_{Total} (Gas Side)	kW	25.3532
Q_{Total} (Air Side)	kW	26.3725
Q_{Total} (Recuperator)	kW	25.8628

Effectiveness (Recuperator)	%	39.44
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The relationships, variations between the values of capacity, effectiveness, temperature and flow rate can be stated by the graphics as shown in Fig.. through the use of the experimental data, parameters and results provided by the tables.

Fig.6. Variations of ambient air outlet temperature, T_{a_o} versus exhaust gas inlet temperature, T_{g_i} in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig.7. Variations of exhaust gas outlet temperature, T_{g_o} versus exhaust gas inlet temperature, T_{g_i} in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

As a heat pipe air recuperator design rule, the flow rates for exhaust gas and ambient air are always adjusted approximately equal to each other, that is ($m_g \approx m_a$) during the implementation of experimental tests. Fig.6. shows that ambient air outlet temperatures increase when the exhaust gas inlet temperatures increase. Fig. 7. shows that exhaust gas outlet temperatures also increase when the exhaust gas inlet temperatures increase.

Fig.8. Variations of inlet- outlet temperatures of exhaust gas and ambient air for heat pipe air recuperator, Tgi, Tgo, Tai, Tao ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig.8. shows the variations between the exhaust gas inlet-outlet temperatures, and the ambient air inlet-outlet temperatures. The waste exhaust gas enters the heat pipe air recuperator at a specific temperature and loses out its energy and leaves the recuperator at a lower temperature. On the other hand, the ambient air sent to the recuperator recovers this lost energy and leaves the recuperator at a higher temperature than the inlet temperature rate. Therefore, an energy transfer is realized between the waste exhaust gases and ambient air by means of heat pipe air recuperator system. Apart from that, the variation graphics mentioned on Fig. 8. also shows that the variations are realized as expected and the heat pipe air recuperator is working properly.

Fig.9. Variations of exhaust gas flow rate, m_g , versus exhaust gas inlet temperature, T_{g_i} in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig.10. Variations of ambient air flow rate, m_a , versus exhaust gas inlet temperature, T_{g_i} in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig.9 states that the exhaust gas flow rates decrease by the exhaust gas inlet temperatures increase on condition that the recuperator capacity remains constant. Fig.10 states the variations of ambient air flow rate by the exhaust gas inlet temperature increase.

Fig.11. Variations of recuperator capacity, Q_{Total} versus exhaust gas inlet temperature, T_{g_i} in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig.12. Variations of recuperator effectiveness, E versus exhaust gas inlet temperature, T_{g_i} in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig. 11 states that the total recuperator capacity values increase by the exhaust gas inlet temperatures increase, Fig.12 states that the recuperator effectiveness rates increase by the exhaust gas inlet temperatures increase on condition that $m_g \approx m_a$ and the exhaust gas outlet temperatures and ambient air inlet temperatures are kept constant.

Fig.13. Variations of recuperator capacity, Q_{Total} versus ambient air outlet temperature, Ta_o in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$)

Fig.14. Variations of recuperator effectiveness, E versus ambient air outlet temperature, Ta_o in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig. 13 states that the total recuperator capacity rates increase by the ambient air outlet temperatures increase, Fig.14 states that the recuperator effectiveness rates increase by the ambient air outlet temperatures increase on condition that $m_g \approx m_a$ and the exhaust gas outlet temperatures and ambient air inlet temperatures are kept constant.

Fig.15. Variations of recuperator capacity, Q_{Total} versus exhaust gas flow rate, m_g in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig.16. Variations of recuperator effectiveness, E versus exhaust gas flow rate, m_g in accordance with the test results ($m_g \approx m_a$).

Fig.15 states that the total recuperator capacity rates increase by the exhaust gas flow rates increase, Fig. 16 states that the recuperator effectiveness rates increase by the exhaust gas flow rates increase on condition that $m_a = \text{constant}$ and, the exhaust gas inlet-outlet temperatures and the ambient air outlet temperatures are kept constant.

Thus, under the similar conditions (the exhaust gas inlet-outlet temperatures and the ambient air outlet temperatures are kept constant); if lower ambient air inlet temperatures occur, the exhaust gas flow rates should be increased, ambient air flow rates should be kept constant in order to prevent the decrease of recuperator effectiveness. Another approach of parametric variation can be described as follows: on condition that the exhaust gas inlet-outlet temperatures and the ambient air inlet temperatures are kept constant and the exhaust gas flow rates, total recuperator capacity rates are continuously kept constant, the ambient air outlet temperatures and, so the recuperator effectiveness rates shall increase if the ambient air flow rates decrease.

CONCLUSION

1. In accordance with the general design rule; on condition that mass flow rate of waste exhaust gas is equal to the mass flow rate of ambient air to be heated, and the outlet temperature of waste exhaust gas and inlet temperature of ambient air are constant, as the inlet temperature of waste exhaust gas gets higher the capacity of heat pipe air recuperator also gets higher.
2. On condition that the mass flow rate of exhaust gas is equal to the mass flow rate of ambient air, the outlet temperature of exhaust gas and the inlet temperature of ambient air are constant, if the inlet temperature of exhaust gas gets higher the effectiveness of recuperator also gets higher.
3. As the inlet temperature of exhaust gas approach to the outlet temperature, both the capacity and effectiveness rates of recuperator decrease considerably. Therefore, it is necessary to avoid such an application. That is, the inlet temperature of exhaust gas must not be decreased significantly, in other words, the inlet temperature of exhaust gas must not be approached to the outlet temperature value.
4. In order to keep constant, the capacity rate of recuperator; on condition that the outlet temperature of waste exhaust gas and the inlet temperature of ambient air are constant in any case, if the inlet temperature rates of exhaust gas decrease gradually, both the flow rates of exhaust gas and ambient air must equally be increased.
5. On condition that the outlet temperature of waste exhaust gas and the inlet temperature of ambient air are constant in any case, in order to provide increasing ambient air outlet temperature rates versus decreasing exhaust gas inlet temperature rates, the ambient air flow rates must be decreased and the exhaust gas flow rates must be kept constant. Under these circumstances, the recuperator effectiveness rates shall increase. Such an operating condition is appropriate if ambient air flow rate is required to decrease.
6. On condition that the inlet –outlet temperatures of exhaust gas and the inlet temperature of ambient air are kept constant in any case, in order to provide increasing ambient air outlet temperature rates, the ambient air flow rate must be decreased and exhaust gas flow rate must be kept constant. However, during this application, the decreasing rate of ambient air is not a sharp drop as much introduced by above conclusion-item 5. Therefore, the total capacity rates remain constant and the effectiveness rates increase.
7. If the outlet-inlet temperatures of exhaust gas and the inlet-outlet temperatures of ambient air are always kept constant, and if the flow rates of both exhaust gas and ambient air are equally increased, therefore, the capacity rates increase.
8. If all the temperature rates indicated by above conclusion-item 7 are kept constant at the design values, the maximum flow rates of exhaust gas and ambient air to be used in order to increase the capacity rate, must be equal to the flow rates accepted for design conditions.
9. The most appropriate capacity and effectiveness results for the heat pipe air recuperator are obtained when the operating conditions approach the design values.
10. Due to the reason mentioned by above conclusion-item 9, it is necessary to operate the system by adjusting all the variable parameters of heat pipe air recuperator as much as close, even equal to the design values, in order to provide the most appropriate results.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data available on request from the author;

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [Emin Taner ELMAS, ETE], upon reasonable request.

Policy: Basic, Share upon Request.

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